

ESIP Community Report: Impact of Community Fellows Program

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Executive Summary

The ESIP Community Fellows Program has had a strong and lasting impact on early-career Earth science data professionals, particularly in shaping career trajectories, expanding professional networks, and strengthening confidence and belonging in the field. Survey responses from 23 alumni show that all respondents experienced at least some career influence from the Fellowship, with nearly half reporting that it had “quite a bit” or “a great deal” of impact. Most alumni are now working in academia (74%) or government (22%), and many credit the Fellowship with starting new collaborations, taking on leadership roles (61% each), and expanding into interdisciplinary or data-intensive work (44%). Fellows also report that the program helped clarify career interests (74%), strengthen professional networks and CVs (70%), and increase interest in Earth science data work (65%).

The program’s greatest value comes from community engagement, particularly participation in ESIP Meetings, networking opportunities, mentorship, and access to leaders in the field. All respondents report that the Fellowship expanded their professional network, with more than half indicating significant growth. Alumni consistently describe the Fellowship as a source of belonging, mentorship, and interdisciplinary community that helped them navigate career decisions and access new opportunities. Many emphasize that the relationships and confidence built through the program are among the most meaningful outcomes, often influencing job placements, leadership development, and long-term professional identity. These findings demonstrate that the Community Fellows Program is a high-impact investment in the next generation of Earth science data professionals and provides strong evidence for its continuation and support.

Introduction

About ESIP Community Reports

ESIP is a home for Earth science data professionals. As a nonprofit funded by cooperative agreements with NASA, NOAA, and USGS, we bring together interdisciplinary collaborations to share technical knowledge and engage with data users. Community reports are published to respond to community needs, ensure organizational transparency, and to raise awareness on topics relevant to our partners and community members. In some cases, a synthesis report will be published to examine trends in community activities over time. **This report summarizes findings from a survey we sent out to alumni of our Community Fellows Program (2011-2024).**

Community Fellows Program Overview

The Community Fellows Program, previously known as the Student Fellows Program, was established as an opportunity within ESIP for early career researchers to work closely with professionals in an interdisciplinary, cross-sector group by working with one of the ESIP Collaboration Areas. In this role, Fellows also offer support running the January and July ESIP Meetings alongside ESIP staff. They receive a \$2,000 stipend, registration for both Meetings, and travel support to attend the in-person Meeting.

The Community Fellows program has been a part of ESIP since 2011. Over the years, the number of Fellows has shifted with there being ten Fellows in the last two years (Table 1). There have been evident positive outcomes from the Program over time, but there has never been a formal evaluation to assess those outcomes.

Table 1. Number of Fellows participating in the Program since data were recorded.

Year	# of Fellows
2019	9
2020	7
2021	8
2022	9
2023	8
2024	10
2025	10

Community Fellows Alumni Survey Distribution

Over time, as Fellows change institutions or take new jobs, it can be difficult to maintain updated contact information. We pulled together affiliations and emails available from our past records and then conducted a web search to get updated contact information for Fellows since their Fellowship ended. We found contact information for 47 past Fellows who were part of the Program between 2011 and 2024. We then sent out a request for these individuals to complete a short survey (reference Appendix) to collect data on the potential impact that the program has had on them personally and professionally.

Findings

Of the 47 individuals contacted, we had four email bouncebacks. Of those who received the survey, 23 responded (a 53% response rate).

Influence of Fellowship on Career Path

We found that most respondents are working in academia, and a quarter are working in government roles (Table 2). Some have obtained positions in the nonprofit and private sectors while others are currently self-employed (Table 2).

Table 2. Percentage of past Fellows currently working in different sectors.

Current Work Sector	Percentage
Academia	74%
Government	22%
Nonprofit	13%
Private sector	9%
Self-employed / consulting	9%
Finishing up PhD program	4%

All respondents indicated that the Fellowship had at least “a little” influence over their career path, with 30% indicating that it had “quite a bit” of an influence and 17% indicating that it had “a great deal” of influence (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Percentage of respondents indicating to what extent the Program influenced their career path.

Respondents shared specific ways in which the Fellowship has influenced their careers. More than half (61%) indicated that they started a new collaboration, presented at a professional meeting, or took on leadership roles (Table 3). Others indicated that the Fellowship supported them securing a job or new position (39%) or receiving a promotion or advancement (13%; Table 3). ESIP is considered a home to Earth data science professionals which may be why 44% of respondents indicated that participation in the Fellowship resulted in their expanding into data-intensive or interdisciplinary work (Table 3).

Two respondents selected “other,” responding that the Program supported their “admittance into a PhD program (initially participated as MS student)” and their “presenting talks on collaborative cluster work.”

Table 3. Percentage of respondents (N=23) indicating in what ways the Fellowship influenced their career path.

Type of influence	Percentage
Started a new collaboration	61%
Presented at a professional meeting or conference	61%
Took on leadership roles	61%
Expanded into data-intensive or interdisciplinary work	44%

Type of influence	Percentage
Secured a job or new position	39%
Published a paper, report, or other product	39%
Joined a new professional community or network	39%
Received a promotion or advancement	13%
None of the above	4%

Outcomes of the Fellowship

This is the first time ESIP has assessed how Fellows have been impacted by their participation in the Fellowship Program. A key piece of information gained from this survey is that all respondents experienced at least one positive outcome from their experience (Table 4). Areas of strong impact included solidifying their career path through clarifying career interests (74%), increasing interest in Earth science data work (65%), strengthening their sense of belonging in the field (57%), and exploring careers beyond traditional academia (30%; Table 4). Other outcomes included growing professional networks, building a CV, and securing a future career opportunity (Table 4).

Two respondents selected "other," responding that the Fellowship "helped me realize that I was interested in applications of data more than data management itself" and "helped me learn about better open science practices and become aware of the many ways people engage with these topics."

Table 4. Percentage of respondents (N=23) indicating which of the following outcomes they experienced during their time in the Fellowship Program.

Type of influence	Percentage
Clarified my career interests	74%
Strengthened my professional network	70%
Strengthened my CV/resume	70%
Increased my interest in Earth science data work	65%
Increased my interest in interdisciplinary collaboration	61%
Strengthened my sense of belonging in the field	57%

Type of influence	Percentage
Helped me build confidence in pursuing new opportunities	44%
Helped me explore careers beyond traditional academia	30%
Helped me secure a job, internship, fellowship, or postdoc	17%
Did not influence my career path	0%

Personal and Professional Development

We asked to what extent the Fellowship contributed to the Fellows’ development. There are only four areas where a respondent indicates “not at all” (Table 5). More than half indicated significant development in the areas of professional networking (65%) and confidence in engaging with professionals (52%; Table 5).

Table 5. Percentage of respondents (N=23) indicating to what extent the Fellowship contributed to their personal or professional development in the following areas.

Areas of development	Not at all	A little or Somewhat	Quite a bit or a great deal
Professional networking	0%	52%	65%
Confidence in engaging with professionals	4%	44%	52%
Sense of professional identity	4%	43%	48%
Interdisciplinary collaboration	0%	57%	43%
Leadership skills	4%	48%	43%
Understanding of career pathways in the field	4%	52%	39%
Data-related skills or thinking	0%	61%	39%

Value of Fellowship

We also wanted to understand what opportunities bring the most value to the Fellowship. ESIP Meeting participation stood out, with 70% of respondents indicating its value (Table 6). The ability to engage with others in the community was also of value with 57% indicating networking opportunities, and 44% indicating mentorship and access to

leaders in the field as valuable to them (Table 6). Professional development activities were given a low value ranking (13%; Table 6), but this may be related to the lack of focus on professional development training in the current program. One respondent selected “other,” responding “access to seed funding through Funding Friday and ESIP Lab” as an opportunity with value to Fellows.

Table 6. Percentage of respondents indicating which Fellowship opportunities were most valuable. Respondents could select up to three of the options listed.

Fellowship opportunities	Percentage
ESIP Meeting participation	70%
Networking opportunities	57%
Mentorship	44%
Access to leaders in the field	44%
Peer cohort/community	39%
Exposure to career pathways	17%
Professional development activities	13%

Professional network

Because building a Fellows’ professional network is an important part of the Program, we asked to what extent the Program expanded respondents’ professional network. They all indicated some expansion in their network, with 52% indicating a significant expansion (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Percentage of respondents indicating to what extent the Program expanded their professional network.

Testimonials

When asked, "In your own words, what is the most important impact the Fellowship had on you?" we received the following responses (Note: names added with permission):

"Strengthening my earth science community connections." -Qian Huang

"I developed the network that secured my current position."
-Anonymous

"ESIP provided me with true community. I built collaborations and friendships with other fellows, and found mentors in the broader ESIP community. It provided a rare home for interdisciplinary work."
- Anonymous

"Getting to know the great people of ESIP." -Jake Gearon

"I was new to the Earth science data professionals world when I started my Fellowship. The Fellowship gave me credibility and recognition at a time when I was working to establish a network of colleagues as a newcomer in the field. Being an ESIP Fellow helped facilitate networking with professionals close to my interests and from across ESIP. Being able to attend the ESIP meeting was crucial exposure to the breadth of topics and collaborations that ESIP has to offer." -Natalie Raia

"ESIP's community of passionate earth science data practitioners solidified my interest in working for a government agency or nonprofit. I wish I could say it also helped me pursue that path, but the ongoing challenges with finding that work are out of ESIP's control. In other circumstances, the opportunity to network throughout the fellowship would have been very helpful. I participated during the COVID years when the meetings were strictly virtual, but attending the in-person summer meeting would have made the fellowship even more impactful. I hope that continues to be funded going forward!" - Anonymous

"I gained access to a great community of people, including senior leaders, who I otherwise wouldn't have had a chance to meet. Everyone is so open, kind, and enthusiastic about the work they do. Even though I don't directly engage with the community in my work now, it has helped me land where I am now and I know I can rely on it for opportunities, support, and collaborations with like-minded people." -Sruti Modekurty

"The most meaningful impact was the sense of belonging. As a nontraditional graduate student and Coast Guard veteran, I didn't always feel like I fit the mold. But my fellow ESIP Fellows—exceptional scientists—welcomed me without hesitation and made me feel like I belonged." - Anonymous

"Attending the ESIP meeting and being able to have a series of conversations with folks from all over academia and government." - Anonymous

"The Fellowship allowed me to travel to Asheville for the ESIP Conference in-person, which was an incredible experience. At the conference I was encouraged to network with other fellows, participants, and ESIP leadership. It was nice to be in a small conference setting and get used to presenting a poster!" -Colette Reifsnyder-Brown

"The ESIP student fellowship had a major impact on my career. It gave me a chance to connect with a community of people I never would have met otherwise and made me feel like I truly belonged in this field. The connections I built with my cohort were a huge support system that helped me get through my dissertation and

those first few years of my early career. Now, I feel so much more confident passing these skills down to my own students and helping them find their own way.” - Tom Narock

“It helped realize and emphasized how little interest I had in computers, and expanded the scope at which I think about data” - Jim Coll

“As an international student, this was my first time working with senior professionals (professors, scientists and researchers) from across the US. The fellowship boosted my confidence and contributed a great deal towards my professional development. ESIP basically provided me a platform to connect with like-minded people in Earth Informatics and Data Science, which I wouldn't have gotten otherwise, specially in the post-pandemic times.” - Sahara Ali

“It's been a while since my Fellowship and being part of ESIP, but looking back, I can always remember and appreciate the community - the opportunity to see and learn all the different ways that the ESIP members care about Earth Sciences and how they contribute their own unique, innovative ways to work together to advance our community as a whole.” - Anonymous

“I gained experience leading and organizing meetings and giving professional presentations while participating in a supportive network of peers.” - Anonymous

“I feel that the most important impact was being exposed to the huge range of expertise in the Earth science data field that I would have been unlikely to interact with in academia alone.” - Daniel Segessenman

“I was incredibly lucky to be mentored by kind, smart, and encouraging people who helped me explore science, software, and policy angles that are completely unique to ESIP. I was trusted to take on leadership roles, and I was coached on how to be a better leader. The latter is maybe the most important aspects of mentorship I received. Overall, this is one of the most impactful opportunities I had as a PhD student, and I feel genuinely lucky to have participated.” - Nic Weber

"ESIP Community Fellowship gave me a window into the informatics community and everyone in the community has been so welcoming to me as a graduate students. The fellowship really helped me to expand my professional network and connected with different mentors in the community even after the fellowship. It's fair to say that ESIP fellowship changed my career trajectory." - Yuhan "Douglas" Rao

"The Community Fellowship was a key part of my professional development and career exploration. ESIP introduced me to how to take my data science skills towards understanding the community and infrastructure that supports data and scientific information. The connections I made with other ESIP fellows, community members, and partner organizations has supported me throughout my career and shaped my trajectory as a scientist in ways I could not have anticipated and that I am extremely grateful for." - Alexis Garretson

"Awareness of professional organizations, experience in supporting professional meetings, and really thinking about issues of open science and diving into the ethics of how we conduct science and handle data." - Anonymous

Conclusions

The Community Fellows Program has been supported by ESIP since 2011. These findings indicate that most Fellows who have gone through the Program have experienced positive outcomes.

Specifically, the Program had direct impacts on respondents' choice in career path. This was supported through collaborations initiated within ESIP and exposure to professionals serving in diverse roles across multiple sectors. In some cases, participation in the Program resulted in individuals finding a specific career opportunity.

Related, these findings indicate that the Fellowship improves self efficacy by providing a sense of professional identity and strengthening a sense of belonging in the field while also increasing confidence in engaging with professionals. Strengthening identity and building confidence empowers individuals to pursue opportunities that may have previously felt outside of their abilities.

The ability to engage with the community through Collaboration Area work and attendance at ESIP Meetings is one of the greatest benefits of the Fellowship Program. All respondents indicate growth in their professional network as a result of their participation

and how that network has supported their career journey. Moving forward, these findings can be directly applied to further support development and evaluation of the Community Fellows Program while providing evidence of the impacts the Program has had on early career Earth science data professionals.

Appendix

ESIP Community Fellows Program Alumni Survey

Thank you for taking this short survey (5–7 minutes). Your responses will help us understand how the ESIP Community Fellowship has impacted participants' careers and communicate the program's value to future sponsors and partners.

1. When did you participate in the ESIP Fellowship Program?

[Dropdown or open response]

2. What sector do you currently work in? Select all that apply

- Academia
- Government
- Nonprofit
- Private sector
- Self employed / consulting
- Not currently employed
- Other: [open response]

3. What is your current job title or role? [open response]

4. Overall, how much did the ESIP Community Fellowship influence your career path?

- Not at all
- A little
- Somewhat
- Quite a bit
- A great deal

4. In what ways did the Fellowship influence your career or professional development?

Select all that apply.

- Clarified my career interests
- Helped me explore careers beyond traditional academia
- Increased my interest in Earth science data work
- Increased my interest in interdisciplinary collaboration
- Helped me build confidence in pursuing new opportunities
- Helped me secure a job, internship, fellowship, or postdoc
- Strengthened my professional network
- Strengthened my CV/resume
- Strengthened my sense of belonging in the field
- Did not influence my career path

- Other: [open response]

5. Since participating, which of the following outcomes have you experienced that you associate (at least in part) with the Fellowship? Select all that apply.

- Secured a job or new position
- Received a promotion or advancement
- Started a new collaboration
- Presented at a professional meeting or conference
- Published a paper, report, or other product
- Took on leadership roles
- Expanded into data-intensive or interdisciplinary work
- Joined a new professional community or network
- None of the above
- Other: [open response]

6. How much did the Fellowship contribute to your development in the following areas?

Matrix: Not at all / A little / Somewhat / Quite a bit / A great deal

- Professional networking
- Interdisciplinary collaboration
- Confidence engaging with professionals
- Understanding of career pathways in the field
- Data-related skills or thinking
- Leadership skills
- Sense of professional identity

7. Which aspects of the Fellowship were most valuable to you? Select up to 3.

- Mentorship
- ESIP Meeting participation
- Networking opportunities
- Exposure to career pathways
- Professional development activities
- Access to leaders in the field
- Peer cohort/community
- Other: [open response]

8. Did the Fellowship expand your professional network?

- Yes, significantly
- Yes, somewhat
- A little

- Not at all

9. In your own words, what is the most important impact the Fellowship had on you?

[Open response]

10. May we use your response as a testimonial in reports or sponsor materials?

- Yes, with my name
- Yes, anonymously
- No

[If "yes, with my name is selected]

Please share your name to add your name to your testimonial. If you would like to keep your other responses anonymous, you can email your testimonial directly to community@esipfed.org.